

Purposive and Literal Approaches in the Judicial Application of *Maṣlaḥah*: An Overview

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Abstract

Maṣlaḥah is the jurisprudential principle that does not stand alone in its application. It must be integrated with other *uṣūl al-fiqh* instruments, for example, *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah*, *sad al-dharā'i'*, *istiḥsān* and et cetera. The combination will put *maṣlaḥah* to be applied within the purview of several approaches like purposive, literal, preventive, and *istiḥsanīc*, and many more. The judge will then adopt those approaches in the judicial field in applying *maṣlaḥah* to deliver the judicial judgment for the case. The present paper is prepared to discuss the practical processes that the judges may invoke in the application of *maṣlaḥah* for judicial determinations. There are many approaches, but this paper will focus on the literal and purposive techniques. The Malaysian Court's practice will also be attended.

Keywords: Purposive, Literal, Approaches, *Maṣlaḥah*, Judicial, Application.

INTRODUCTION

One of the ingredients of judicial ruling is the ground of judgment. The ground of decision is also known as legal reasoning or *ratio decidendi*. The latter is considered a jurisprudential ground of the *fiqh* rules, which comes from the primary and secondary sources of *sharia* through *uṣūl al-fiqh* methodology. Legal reasoning by the judge differs from the reasoning of the jurist (*mujtahid*). The former, meanwhile, bears a resemblance to the latter in some situations. Still, it is more about a reason for selecting jurist finding or codified law in other problems because the scope of the judicial task is to apply them in actual cases. More often than not, legal reasoning also encompasses interpreting the intended meaning of the codified law.

In whatever situation, be it in the form of deduction of rules from the *sharia*'s sources or selection, interpretation, and application of codified law, *maṣlaḥah* can be a guiding factor that eventually becomes the reason for the judgment. Najibah Mat Zin stressed that upholding *maṣlaḥah* should be one of the crucial considerations in interpreting the codified law, and this approach is unquestionably consistent with the spirit of *maqāṣid al-shariaḥ Maslahah* in the form of legal reasoning that can demonstrate how the judicial activism can connect with the need of the society and solve its problem.

Maṣlaḥah is a principle that does not stand alone in its application. Other *uṣūl al-fiqh* instruments inevitably join it, for example, *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah*, *sad al-dharā'i'*, *istiḥsān* and et cetera. The combination will place *maṣlaḥah* to be applied within the framework of several approaches like purposive, literal, *istiḥsanīc*, and many more. The judge will then adopt those approaches in the judicial field in applying *maṣlaḥah* to provide the judicial judgment for the case.

METHOD

This paper may be regarded as library base research or content base research. It will be purely doctrinal and qualitative. Hence, this research will use two principal methodologies: data collection and data analysis. Various types of data from multiple sources will be collected and filtered in data collection. The data includes primary, secondary, direct, and indirect data. In data analysis methodology, three methods are applied: inductive, deductive, and comparative.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Preservation of *Maṣlaḥah* in the Purposive Approach

The approach envisioned to attend to the purpose of something is regarded as a purposive approach. In the context of Islamic legal theory, the objective refers to what is intended by *sharia* (jurisprudentially known as *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah*). Thus the purposive approach connotes the approach which is grounded on *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah*. The judge will determine *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* to be achieved in contemplating his decision. In Common Law, the purposive approach is discussed within the ambit of rules of interpretation. There are several recognized approaches, one known as the purposive rule. It means a practice that seeks to interpret the provision by ascertaining the parliament's purposes in legislating the particular legislation or particular provision.

There is a clear differentiation line between the concept of purposive approach in Islamic legal theory and Common Law. They differ in terms of scope of the function in which the Common Law's purposive approach is only limited to construing the statute. On the other hand, the purposive approach in Islamic legal theory holds broader scope where it is not confined to the just rule of interpretation but also a device to deduce the new law based on the general principle which is extracted from the *naṣ* and a mechanism to select and apply the established *sharia* rule.

In the Islamic judicial sphere, the purposive approach must also not be restricted as finding, appreciating, and implementing *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* only. Still, it must preserve the purpose of codified law, which is respected in the intention of the lawmaker provided that the law does not infringe *sharī'a* rules and ideals. In the case of *Pendakwa Syarie Negeri Selangor v Khalid bin Abdul Samad*, the court asserted that the court might refer to the lawmaker's intent in construing the law.

Thus in the present paper's viewpoint, the purposive approach connotes a judicial *ijtihād* (*al-ijtihād al-qaḍā'i*) by the judge through an approach to preserve *maṣlaḥah* through the preservation of *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* or intention of the legislator of codified law. The approach can also be regarded as *al-ijtihād al-qaḍā'i al-maqāṣidī* (judicial *ijtihād* based on the purposes of the law).

The intention of the codified lawmaker is inevitably considered in the purposive approach because they are the ruler or the representative of the ruler, and the ruler's action is undoubtedly based on *maṣlaḥah*. This is understood from the maxim:

تصرفات الإمام منوطة بالمصلحة

Meaning: The actions of the ruler is based on *maṣlaḥah*

The maxim provides that the action of the ruler, in terms of imposition or prohibition, must secure and protect the interest of the people either in worldly or religious matters. The step of the ruler comprises the law-making and its imposition, which is done, among others, by the judge appointed by him. Hence the maxim indirectly obliges the judge to ponder *maṣlaḥah* in his judgment in which will inevitably put the judge in a position to take a *maṣlaḥah* approach. The adage is not unconditional but subject to certain restrictions. One of them is that the ruler and the judge must not abandon the rights of the public, like the right to maintain the execution of a killer who has no *wali* because they are mere their representation. Their power, therefore, is not absolute. The eventual restriction is there must be no conflict with the definite *naṣ* (*naṣ qat'ī*).

Further, in the Malaysian context, the aim of the lawmaker can be found expressly in the Hansard of Parliament. If the expression is absent, the lawmaker's intention can be found by implication. When the meaning is extracted through substance, it is also a *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* deriving process because the codified law is legislated based on *maṣlaḥah* as enunciated in the said maxim. It may be argued that, based on the said maxim, the whole codified law is viewed as *maṣlaḥah*. Hence, there is no necessity to highlight the intention of the maker. This is the proper observation, but on certain occasions, the judge's literal reading of the statute may not serve the purpose of the codified law like the case of the literal reading of *naṣ*. As a result, it may indirectly disregard the *maṣlaḥah* of the people or the litigating parties.

The judge will look into the *sharia*'s purpose in the purposive approach. They can be either general purpose or a specific purpose related to the particular subject matter. The former involves the *maqāṣid 'āmmah* like *al-'adl* (justice), *al-taysīr* (facility), *al-ḥurriyyah* (freedom) and others which are derived from the general *dalīl* or *naṣ kulliy*. In the latter, the subject matters mean the matters under the court's jurisdiction. In the Malaysia Shariah Court, the judge has jurisdiction ranging from family, property, and criminal cases.

The main *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* behind the rules that govern the family matters is to protect the lineage, its dignity and to preserve the continuous reproduction practice (*al-tanāsul*). Al-Shāṭibī further opined that the reproduction is the utmost and original *maqāṣid* for the marriage regulation. The marriage (including polygamy) itself, then, is a *wasīlah* to attain the said *maqāṣid*. Besides, the *maqāṣid al-sharī'ah* behind the marriage rules are to realize self-tranquillity, inner peace, honest dealing, and honest communication between husband and wife. Most *fuqahā'* opined that the purpose of marriage is self-peacefulness, *izdiwāj* (the state of being paired), placing the women to be taken care of and putting the woman under protection.

The *maqāṣid*, as mentioned earlier, is about *al-maqāṣid al-kulliyah* in marriage scope. For *al-maqāṣid al-juziyyah* behind the *sharia* rules on marriage, they are plentiful because there is a variety of sub-subjects under the marriage like dowry, *wilāyah* (the authority to marry others), *walīmah* (wedding reception), and others which considerable numbers of *al-maqāṣid al-juziyyah*. As a case in point, the *maqāṣid* in putting *walī* as a condition for the valid marriage is firstly to differentiate *sharī'a* compliant marriage from other kinds of marriage. Secondly, the need is required to preserve the nobility of women from being subject to impudence resulting from their activities in marrying themselves. The third *maqāṣid* is to protect the woman from the irresponsible and unreliable husband. Last but not least, the *maqāṣid* behind the condition is to preserve the social relationship between families.

In Islam, the dowry is a wife's absolute right. The dowry also works as an instrument to maintain and last the relationship between husband and wife. The dowry is regulated by *sharia* as a sign of respect and love of the husband to his wife. Furthermore, it is held for the dowry to distinguish the Islamic marriage from the *jāhiliyyah* tradition, which permitted the husband to take away the wife's dowry. Besides, *sharia* has also been forbidden to announce the wedding publicly. The main *maqāṣid* behind it is to protect the dignity of the husband, wife, and the lineage because the announcement can eradicate any doubt on the relationship of the husband and wife. It indirectly encourages and inspires the other individual to marry and live in purity and faithfulness. It also can obliquely shield society from the rampant false sexual accusation and innuendo, which can disrupt the public order.

Pertaining the divorce, it is permissible in Islam as a final solution for the marriage crisis. *Sharia* realized that the marriage could not provide continuous happiness, mercy, and peacefulness between wife and husband. Hence, *ṭalāq* is regulated to tolerate the dissolution of marriage during *ḍarūrah*. The *ṭalāq* with no valid reason is prohibited, and Allah S.W.T forbids the smell of the paradise to the wife who demands *ṭalāq* from her husband. The *maqāṣid* behind the *ṭalāq* is to protect the marriage from any intolerable internal adversities after all efforts are endeavored to put them to an end. This is the general *maqāṣid* of *ṭalāq*.

In the *maqāṣid juziyyah* aspect, *sharia* has made a rule regarding the available numbers of *ṭalāq* in which the third *ṭalāq* is considered the final one where the husband can not *ruj'ū* (return) to his wife unless the wife married another man and having sexual intercourse. The *maqāṣid* behind this number of *ṭalāq* is to offer the opportunity to the husband to reunite with the wife because sometimes the *ṭalāq* is pronounced without conscience and with no driving purpose. The regulation on the third *ṭalāq* is to avoid *ṭalāq* from being as a playful and insult tool of the husband. Further, *maqāṣid juziyyah*, behind the *'iddah* rule, ensures the wife's womb is free from any expected child. If there is an expected child, then it can be a factor for the husband to think about the reunion with the wife for the sake of the child's future.

Further, on the *mu'āmalah māliyah* (property dealings), Ibnu' Āshūr has enlisted several *maqāṣid kulliyah*. This *maqāṣid* can be comprehended through the encouragement of *sharia* to do property dealing and the commands of *sharia* on the legality of the property transaction. Firstly, *sharia* rules behind *mu'āmalah māliyah* are to make sure the wealth is circulated to as many people as possible. The circulation is commanded by *sharia* through charitable (*tabarr'u*) and commercial dealings. The commands include the requirement on the witness, the proper record, the clear offer and acceptance, and many more.

Secondly, *sharia* purposes in *mu'āmalah māliyah* are to ensure the protection and clarity of properties (*wuḍūh wa ḥifẓ al-ammwāl*). It means a property transaction must be explicit as it can avoid any enmity, hatred, and *ḍarār*. This is why "*tarāḍin*" (willingness) or mutual consent between the parties is emphasized by *sharia*. The willingness can curb the potential enmity that might happen in the future. The law on *al-rahnu* (guaranty) in debt is regulated by *sharia* is also an indication of the importance of security to avoid any anticipated *ḍarār* to one of the parties.

Thirdly, another purpose of *sharia* behind *mu'āmalah māliyah* rules is to confirm and certify the ownership of the property (*ithbāt al-amwāl*). For this *maqāṣid*, *sharia* has emphasized the protection and specification of the request of one or several entities by devising several mechanisms, for instance, sale transaction, *ijārah*, and *isti'jār*, and others. Through the said mechanisms, the ownership is acknowledged and can not be apprehended by any means. Under this *maqāṣid* also, *sharia* has safeguarded the rights of the property owner to exploit or use his property without any intervention. However, the exercise of the request must not cause harm to the owner of the others. In this respect, *sharia* imposed *al-ḥajr* (impediment) on those declared as *safih* as a legal mechanism to avoid the disabled owner from harming himself in dealing with his property. Besides, *sharia* has also forbidden usury because it enriches the rich at the expense of the desperate conditions of the poor. It harms society because the richer become more prosperous, and the poor keep oppressed financially by the burden of unfair compounded debt. Under this *maqāṣid* also, the intervention on other's property is regarded unlawful and can be penalized under civil remedy or criminal punishment.

Not least of all, the purpose behind *sharia mu'āmalah māliyah* is fair and just dealing. Just dealing is established through legal transactions or succession. In this regard, *sharia*, for instance, has precluded the monopoly in the food business. *Sharia* allowed the government to take stern action on monopoly activity like Umar said, "no monopoly in our market."

Furthermore, like marriage, *maqāṣid juziyyah* in *mu'āmalah māliyah* also can be observed in its every sub-subject like *hibah* (gift), *waqf* (endowment), sale, *ijārah* (leasing), and the likes. Eventually, every subject will form a vast and countless numbers of *maqāṣid juziyyah*. For the sake of the present paper, the *maqāṣid juziyyah* behind *waqf* rules only will be attended in detail as a representative example of *maqāṣid juziyyah* in *mu'āmalah māliyah*. The utmost *maqāṣid* in *sharia* rule regarding *waqf* is to protect "the *waqf*" itself (*ḥifz al-waqf*). *Waqf* contributes numerous benefits for society. Hence it must be first preserved of its function. This is why the jurists asserted that the revenue of *waqf* property must be first allotted and assigned to protect the property. Under this *maqāṣid* also, the damage on *waqf* property must be repaid if it can be claimed from the transgressor.

Another *maqāṣid* of *waqf* rules is protecting the interest of the beneficiaries (*jalb al-manāfi' li al-mawqūf 'alayh*). Any action related to the *waqf* property will be disapproved if it puts the property at risk of damage or loss. For this reason, the jurists did not allow the *waqf* property to be rented at the discounted rental value. Another *maqāṣid* behind *waqf* rules is avoidance of conflict or hostility. Under this *maqāṣid*, the jurist forbids the shared property for *waqf* unless the partners in the transferred property obtain permission. In addition, *ḥifz al-manfa'ah al-'ammah* (safeguarding the community's interest) is also determined as one of the *maqāṣid* behind *waqf* rules. Anything to be done for *waqf* property must not contradict the claim or benefit of the community. Regarding this *maqāṣid*, the jurist has disallowed any alienation of property made by the ruler from the state's wealth as a private or family *waqf*.

Further, there are three main *maqāṣid al-sharīa* behind their rules in criminal matters. First and foremost, the punishment in criminal cases is intended by *sharia* as edification (*al-ta'dīb*), education, and lesson to the wrongdoer. Edifying and educating a person is considered the highest *maqāṣid* because the process of *al-ta'dīb* can produce a good person who will ultimately form a good society. The highest *al-ta'dīb* is through *ḥudūd* crime because it is regulated by *sharia* for the most severe crime. The heavy punishment is meted out by *sharia* in *ḥudūd* is intended no other than to give the lesson to the criminal and deter the people.

The second *maqāṣid* behind the crime rules is to relieve the crime's victim. The punishment on the culprit can eliminate the victim's perpetual enmity and continuous hatred. Under this *maqāṣid*, *qīṣāṣ* rule is introduced by *sharia* where the victim or his family may retaliate what was inflicted violently on them. The revenge feeling of the victim may threaten public order. The last *maqāṣid* is to deter the public from involving in any crime. Ibnu al-'Arabī said, "the *ḥad* punishment will dissuade the punished wrongdoer, the one who attends and witnesses the execution will learn the lesson and restrain from the crime, and he will also spread the news on the punishment; hence the others will also get educated."

Operationally, in the judicial judgments, the consideration and application of those mentioned purposes of *sharia* by the judge in his determination will constitute a purposive approach. In the case of *Pendakwa Syarie Negeri Selangor v Khalid bin Abdul Samad*, the court stressed that the *maqāṣid* in criminal punishment serves as a lesson to the offender and the society. The discipline also acts as a deterrent to society so as not to commit the same offence. The court, in this case, has embraced the purposive approach in determining the sentence for the accused. The court has decided not to imprison the accused since it is too harsh and the *maqāṣid* behind the crime punishment is not to harm the individual. The court also overruled the request of the accused to be fined not more than RM 2000 only in his mitigation submission. The court

opined that the request is too lighter and will not serve the *maqāsid* of crime punishment. Hence, the court decided the fine of RM2,900 or imprisonment for three months in default for the accused.

On a final note, the judgment of the judge, which is based on *maṣlaḥah* as legal reasoning, can be considered as a purposive approach if it appreciates the *maqāsid al-sharī'ah* and the wisdom of the written law as intended by the legislative body. The application of *maṣlaḥah* by the judge within the purview of *maqāsid al-sharī'ah* bears an exact resemblance, *mutatis mutandis*, to *al-ijtihād al-maqāsidī* by the jurist except it is practiced restrictively in the field of judiciary.

The literal Approach and its Effect on the Preservation of *Maṣlaḥah*

The literal approach is a direct opposite to the purposive approach. In this approach, the legal text's mere apparent and plain meaning has adhered. For most jurists, the literal meaning is a default meaning of the text. Islamic legal theory provides that the literal meaning may come from three aspects, namely, (1) the current language user's ordinary understanding, (2) the grammatical rules of the language, and (3) the language use of a past community which defines the grammatical rules.

Some jurists embrace applying this approach, *mujtahid-muftī*, and judge in approaching the divine scriptures, namely *al-Qurān* and *hadīth*. They are always dubbed as literalist, *textualist*, or Zahirite. It is commonly known that Zahirite represented this approach in Islamic legal literature. However, the practice has essentially not been associated with Zahirite *mazhab* only because the literal paradigm can be found of its application across the *mazhab* through the concept of *'ibārat al-naṣ*, *al-manṭūq*, *mafhūm al-muwāfaqah*, and the likes.

In the fatwa and judicial context, the non-*mujtahid muftī* and judge can embrace this approach in selecting and applying the prevailing opinion among the *fiqh* rules. The jurist's statement in the form of deduced *fiqh* rules is put in preference literally and used to address the *mustaftī* (those who seek *fatwa*) and adjudicating parties, respectively. The detailed reasoning or contextual background of the jurists' opinion in deducing the rules are inadequately examined in this approach. In the judicial context, this approach is also practiced by the judge in construing and applying the codified law by paying no attention to the lawmaker's intention and resisting the temptation to read between the line. However, those who adopt this approach may also argue that their literal approach is what was intended by the lawmaker because the plain wording contains the precise meaning of the apparent wisdom of the lawmaker. The hidden intention should not be touched and speculated.

Principally jurists differed in terms of their approach to literalism. Some of them opine that the literal meaning of the revelatory text and prophetic sayings are inadequate and may misunderstand the actual messages. Some others have considered the literal approach adequate on some occasions but flawed on others. A minority of jurists adopted a strictly literal approach by only confining them to the literal plain and apparent text. This is the general categorization of jurists' opinion regarding literal meaning, but most jurists always have two faces in dealing with *naṣ*. They are usually literalist at some issues, but they tend to read beyond the line of plain word on some other occasions.

Judicially, the literal approach can be a double-edged sword as far as the effect on *maṣlaḥah* appreciation is concerned. It means that both favorable and unfavorable effects may occur as far as *maṣlaḥah* realization is concerned. This situation is realized in the sense that *maṣlaḥah* is already embedded in every *fiqh* rule or regulated law. The embedment is justified by the basic understanding as touched before that *sharia* has no other purpose than preserving the *maṣlaḥah* and the maker of the regulated law (the ruler) is bound to safeguard the *maṣlaḥah* of the people as enshrined in the previous maxim that states, "the actions of the ruler are based on *maṣlaḥah*." Hence the literal approach is supposed can serve the *maṣlaḥah*.

However, in certain circumstances, the direct imposition of the plain meaning may have a harmful effect. This was expounded by al-Shāṭibī in the practice of *taḥqīq al-manāṭ* when there perhaps a clear literal rule but the imposition of the government by the judge can vary based on the background of the person and situation. For instance, the *sharia* rule requires attribution of *'adālah* on a person before he can be qualified to be a witness. In practice, there are many levels of *'adālah* that can be considered ranging from the highest level (*had al-a'alā*) and the lowest level (*had al-adnā*). Thus, this is where the literal reading on *naṣ* seems not adequate but must be coupled with the observation on the situation of

the case and the current state of society. Implementation of the literal rule without enough observation and necessary *ijtihad* of the judge can lead to an illegitimate witness standing in the witness box and causes a miscarriage of justice.

In the case of *Pendakwa Syarie v Razali bin Saaban*, the court has demonstrated how it departed from the literal wording of the legal provision. In this case, the accused was charged for being in the gambling premise, which is considered an offense under section 18 (1) of Syaria Criminal Offence Enactment (Pulau Pinang) 1996. The court, however, did not convict the accused on the ground that for mere being in the premise does not warrant a conviction. The court stressed that the provision must not be read but with the spirit of *sharia* rule. The intention to involve in gambling must be proven. In this case, the prosecutor failed to provide the evidence to show the accused's intent. The court, therefore, believes that it is not safe to convict the accused. The court has taken the right decision because the literal imposition of the section may implicate the person who might not involve in gambling. This is an apparent injustice, and this is not what is intended by *sharia* and regulated law.

In short, the judge may take a literal approach judicially if it is deemed safe to secure the justice, which becomes an essence of *maṣlahah*. Otherwise, he may be in an inevitable position to do *ijtihad* to depart from the literal approach if it does not serve the purposes of *sharia* or the regulated law. The application of *maṣlahah* within the purview of the literal course is seen as reasonable with strict observation on the fact of the case accordingly.

CONCLUSION

Maṣlahah is jurisprudential because the judges can adopt it in their judicial decision. There are many practical approaches available for the judge in materializing *maṣlahah* application, and two of them are purposive and literal approaches. The purposive approach can be realized when the courts take into consideration *maqāsid al-sharī'ah* and the intention of the codified lawmaker. Meanwhile, the court's judgment may also have its *maṣlahah*-based effects through literal approach as long as it does not contradict the *maqāsid al-sharī'ah*.

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